

THIN-PLY COMPOSITE MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURE

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The Multi-Functional Structures (MFS) project objectives:

- Study the integration possibilities of thin-ply MFS layers into high performance principal structures.
- Determination of conductive traces deposition into composites (i.e. ink-jet)
- Evaluation of the structural capabilities and design limitations.
- MFS testing for FEM correlation and functional parts modelling.

Expertise:

- Thin-ply composite materials
- Composite Additive Manufacturing (AM)
- Fast Prototyping

Thin-ply composite airframe structure

Expertise:

- Additive manufacturing
- Multi-material AM (conductive inks)
- Ink-jet printing specialists

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Multi-Functional Structures (MFS) design and manufacturing process:

CONSTRAINTS

Electronic schematic diagram

Geometrical design space

CIRCUIT DESIGN

PCB design traces

PCB Design CAD render

SUBSTRATE PREPARATION

Ink-jet printed circuit (double sided)

Integrated component into PCB

MFS INTEGRATION

Multi-Functional Composite Ply (MFCP) Materials and processing:

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MFCP
MATERIALS &
PROCESSING

Three testing setups to evaluate the multifunctional structure

Data acquisition

- The Load-Displacement-Time data was correlated to the traces resistance and strain gauges data.
- A twin-channel milli-ohm resistance and strain measuring apparatus was developed for this purpose.

Objectives:

- Evaluation of the resistance variation and maximum strain capabilities of the conductive traces
- Thin-ply printed specimen bonded to a QI 3mm pre-cured GFRP plate.
- Two traces per specimen with a **5mm control trace** on the left side.
- Five traces evaluation, 0.4mm, 0.6mm, 1.0mm, 2.0mm and 5.0mm

TESTING
TENSILE

Results:

- Failure of the GFRP composite support prior to the failure of the conductive trace
- On first loading electric resistance does not follow a traditional linear scaling with strain: potential preconditioning effect of the sintered nano silver particles on first load cycle.
- Variations of resistance inside the tolerance limits for electronics
- No significant resistance variation (increase) at high strains, no sign of damage before failure of the composite

Trace resistance = $0.2 \Omega \square$

Test objective

- The three point bending test goal was to evaluate the cyclic response of the conductive traces.
- Three sets of 1500 cycles at 0.5% strain were made and measured

Results

- No degradation observed for the cyclic bending at 0.5%.
- Linear response response between strain and resistance variation in cyclic loading. Potential for sensing applications.

Three point bending setup (conductive traces on tension side)

Rmeter connectors

Cyclic results of traces on GFRP specimen

Test objective

- The Zebra-DCB testing objective was to evaluate the interlaminar fracture toughness between different traces width on a constant 1/3 area.
- Four patterns (a, b, c, d as shown on image) were evaluated with a control length of 30mm
- A “Raw” specimen with no print or treatment was also evaluated as a baseline.

Fracture surface

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TESTING
ZEBRA-DCB

2.5mm traces

5.0mm traces

TESTING
ZEBRA-DCB

Results:

- Reduction of peak load in DCB test, in line with reduction of toughness.
- Fracture alternates within the multifunctional ply and at the interface with ink traces
Reduction of toughness larger than rule of mixture: 30% printed area => 50% of fracture energy
- Potential degradation of substrate during NIR particle sintering process:
substrate exposed to elevated temperature $> T_g$ for a few seconds

**Sufficient toughness for most composite applications,
comparable to CFRP composite laminates in mode I**

MFS “LED Chaser”

- Analogic circuit with 555 + 4017 IC’s
- Printed on MFS substrata
- Components bonded using conductive epoxy adhesives
- Challenging procedure on such small components
- New techniques being developed to automate the process

PCB Layout design

Technology integration: Wingfoil Smart Boom

CFRP tube with MFCP end

Handle head internal cavity

I2C MFCP before integration

Sensing Traces

I2C Bus traces on Internal face

Technology integration: Wingfoil Smart Boom

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WINGFOIL
SMART BOOM

Key Technology Specifications:

1. Thin-Ply High definition in-jet printed conductive traces and circuits
2. Seamless integration into laminate, including CFRP:
multifunctionnal ply thickness with adhesive ~100 microns, very flexible
3. High strength structure and fatigue: compatible with most CFRP applications
4. Multi-layer circuit capabilities, with Z interconnections
5. Type of traces: low power DC bus, digital comm (I2C/SPI), analog signals
6. Strain sensing / crack detection or capacitive / touch-sensitive applications

Mechanical Specifications

- **Max strain** = 1.2 % (laminate failure)
- **Mode I toughness** = 600 J/m²
- **Fatigue life @0.5% strain** > 1500

Electrical Specifications

- **Trace resistance** = 0.2 Ω□
- **Min trace width** = 0.1mm
- **Min Trace Space** = 0.05mm
- **Current** < 250mA
- **Voltage** < 120 Volts DC

Multifunctional inkjet printed composite

Tensile

Bending

- No strength reduction due to the printed traces
- Strains > 1.2% tested with no failure
- Traces can be used as strain gauges once preconditioned

DCB/Mode I

- ERR does not correlate with expected values on Zebra DCB specimens
- NIR treatment and sintering process partially damages the substrate
- Prediction is possible using simple cohesive modeling (no bridging)
- Sufficiently high toughness for most applications

Technology is ready to move to industrial applications !

Questions ?

Zebra-DCB exploded layup

TESTING
ZEBRA-DCB

Cohesive zone modeling

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TESTING
ZEBRA-DCB

FE Modeling:

Code-Aster non-linear statics
3D FE model, 1st order hexa
Element size = 0.75 – 1.25mm

Cohesive law:

Bilinear traction separation

Interface	σ_c [MPa]	G_{IC} [J/m ²]	δ_c [mm]
Printed traces	5	100	1/40 δ_{max}
Composite (raw)	35	1350	1/40 δ_{max}
Composite (printed)	15 - 35	600 - 1350	1/40 δ_{max}

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TESTING
ZEBRA-DCB

Results

Raw specimen

Raw specimen:

Cohesive model with experimental value of G_{ic} matches well the measured load – displacement curve.

5.0mm printed traces

1st hypothesis:

Weak interface properties on printed traces
Same interface properties as raw on composite

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TESTING
ZEBRA-DCB

5.0mm printed traces

2nd hypothesis:

Weak interface properties on printed traces
 Altered interface properties of composite
 Identified Gic composite interface = ~ 800 J/m²

IR sintering of ink
 degrades the GFRP
 printing substrate!

MFS “HydroFoil Wing”

- I2C Digital circuit with Magnetometer and atmospheric sensors
- Digital bus (VCC,GND,Data,CLK)
- Typical Prepreg manufacturing process of layers (visible for demo purposes)

(1) Mould preparation

(2) Pre-preg stacking and debulking

(3-4) Printed substrates integration

(5-6) Layup continuation

(7) Standard composite part curing

(9) Demoulding and trimming to final shape

(10) Electronics integration